

MEMS-Tunable Bilayer Plasmonic Metasurfaces for Dynamic Vortex Wave Plates

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Dynamic metasurfaces (MSs) have emerged as a transformative technology in miniaturized tunable optics, enabling reconfigurable optical responses and opening new avenues for compact, adaptive, and multifunctional optical design. Here, a microelectromechanical system (MEMS)-tunable bilayer MS (MEMS-BMS) is demonstrated for dynamic vortex wave plates (VWPs), achieved by integrating a thin-film piezoelectric MEMS mirror with bilayer plasmonic nanostructures composed of differently sized anisotropic nanobricks oriented in various directions. By electrically actuating the MEMS mirror to precisely tune the MEMS-BMS separation, independent 2D phase control at two distinct separation distances is enabled, allowing dynamic switching of the reflected beam between different vortex modes under circularly polarized light excitation. The switching between vortex beams with topological charges of $l = 2$ and $l = -1$ is achieved with high polarization conversion efficiency ($>80\%$) and a fast response time (9 microseconds), while preserving the output circular polarization state. The developed MEMS-BMS VWP with its high efficiency, fast response, and polarization preservation holds strong potential for advanced applications, including high-resolution imaging, dynamic holography, optical tweezers, optical machining, and beyond.

super-resolution imaging,^[8,9] optical tweezers,^[10,11] and biomedical applications.^[12,13] However, conventional methods for generating vortex beams rely on bulky and intricate optical components such as cylindrical lenses,^[14] spiral phase plates,^[15,16] q-plates,^[17,18] and spatial light modulators (SLM),^[19,20] resulting in impractical and cumbersome optical systems.

Metasurfaces (MSs), composed of planar 2D subwavelength nanostructures, have emerged as a powerful platform for tailoring light fields with unprecedented control over amplitude, phase, polarization, and angular momentum.^[21–23] Their ultrathin nature makes them highly promising for ultracompact and cost-effective optoelectronic modules and systems. While recent advancements resulted in diverse MSs for vortex beam generation,^[24–31] most implementations remain static, limiting their adaptability and functionality. Achieving tunable vortex beams with MSs is very challenging, as it requires efficient and

reconfigurable 2D phase control within an ultrathin, densely packed nanostructured array, while circumventing limitations of dynamic tunability and significant complexity of control.^[32–34] Due to these substantial technical hurdles, most state-of-the-art pixelated MSs are restricted to reconfigurable 1D phase control.^[35–38] Consequently, electrically tunable MSs for

1. Introduction

Vortex beams, renowned for their orbital angular momentum and topologically protected spiral phase profiles, have unlocked exciting opportunities across diverse fields,^[1–3] including high-capacity optical communications,^[4,5] laser machining,^[6,7]

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DOI: 10.1002/lpor.202501406

Figure 1. Working Principle of the MEMS-BMS vortex wave plate (VWP). a) Schematic of the electrically actuated MEMS-BMS VWP for reconfigurable switching between $l = 2$ and $l = -1$ vortex modes, under right-handed circularly polarized (RCP) beam incidence. The polarization handedness is defined as the rotation direction of the electric field vector as observed against the direction of light propagation. b) Schematic of the MEMS-BMS unit cell, consisting of a BMS fabricated on a SiO_2 substrate with an SU8 polymer spacer separating the two MS layers, and a movable gold MEMS mirror. The thicknesses of both MS1 and MS2 layers are specified as $T_{m1} = T_{m2} = 50$ nm, with the optimal SU8 thickness of $T_{\text{SU8}} = 470$ nm. The air gap T_a between the MS2 layer and the MEMS mirror can be finely adjusted by applying a voltage to the MEMS mirror. c,d) MS1 and MS2 unit cells viewed from the top above the x - y plane. The unit cell period is specific as $\Lambda = 450$ nm, with other parameter spaces $[L_{x1}, L_{y1}, \theta_1]$ and $[L_{x2}, L_{y2}, \theta_2]$ corresponding to MS1 and MS2 unit cells, respectively.

high-efficiency and reconfigurable vortex beam generation at optical wavelengths still remain elusive.

In this paper, we design and experimentally demonstrate an electrically tunable vortex wave plate (VWP) based on a thin-film piezoelectric micro-electromechanical (MEMS) integrated bilayer MS (MEMS-BMS) configuration.^[39] The MEMS-BMS VWP leverages the synergistic interplay between flexible BMS design and fine-tuning MEMS capabilities, enabling reconfigurable dual-state phase control in a circular polarization basis, thereby facilitating the generation of switchable vortex beams with distinct topological charges while preserving the circular polarization state. Specifically, we demonstrate a MEMS-BMS VWP that enables switching between vortex beams with topological charges of $l = 2$ and $l = -1$ under the incidence of a right-handed circularly polarized (RCP) beam (Figure 1a). At the design wavelength of 1030 nm, the polarization conversion efficiency reaches 80%, with a switching time of 9 μs .

2. Results

2.1. MEMS-BMS VWP Design

The designed MEMS-BMS consists of a BMS fabricated on a SiO_2 substrate with a polymer SU8 spacer separating the two MS layers, and a movable MEMS gold (Au) mirror (Figure 1b; Figure S1, Supporting Information). By applying an actuation voltage V_m to the bottom MEMS mirror, the air gap (T_a) between the BMS and the MEMS mirror can be finely adjusted, enabling reconfigurable MEMS-BMS operating states and corresponding optical responses. Intuitively, the reconfigurable optical responses stem from how the BMS interacts with the interference field pattern formed by the incoming and reflected light from the movable MEMS mirror. When the air gap is adjusted to “MS2 OFF” state ($T_{a1} \approx k \times \lambda/2$, k is non-negative integers), the

MS2 layer aligns with the interference minima, effectively preventing it from responding to the incoming light (Figures S2–S4, Supporting Information), whereas in the “MS2 ON” state, both BMS layers interact with the light, contributing to the overall optical response of the MEMS-BMS structure. It should be mentioned that in the current MEMS-BMS configuration, we utilized rotated anisotropic MS1 and MS2 meta-atoms to achieve highly efficient dual-state phase control in the cross-polarized channel with circularly polarized incidence (Figure 1c,d).

To implement the MEMS-BMS unit cell design, we define the parameter spaces $[L_{x1}, L_{y1}, \theta_1]$ and $[L_{x2}, L_{y2}, \theta_2]$ for MS1 and MS2 unit cells, respectively (Figure 1c,d), within a unit cell size of $\Lambda = 450$ nm, which is substantially smaller than the designed wavelength of $\lambda = 1030$ nm. The thickness of both MS1 and MS2 meta-atoms is set as $T_{m1} = T_{m2} = 50$ nm. Note that the available design parameters define a 6D parameter space (i.e., $[L_{x1}, L_{y1}, \theta_1]$ and $[L_{x2}, L_{y2}, \theta_2]$). For simplicity, and considering the distinct roles of the MS2 layer in the MEMS-BMS configuration, we propose a two-step MEMS-BMS VWP design process: First, we design the VWP function for generating a vortex beam with $l = 2$ at MEMS-BMS separation of $T_{a1} = 465$ nm ($\approx \lambda/2$), corresponding to the “MS2 OFF” state. In this case, the entire MEMS-BMS response is solely dictated by the MS1 unit cell (Figure 2a), which is also evidenced by the simulated total electric field norm, showing that MS2 remains in a “dark state” (Figure 2d, left). To achieve the desired functionality, we calculated the complex reflection coefficients of the MEMS-BMS as functions of MS1 nanobrick dimensions $[L_{x1}, L_{y1}]$ for different SU8 thicknesses (T_{SU8}), and optimized the nanobrick dimensions to achieve an ideal half-wave plate (HWP) design that exhibits equal reflection amplitudes ($|r_x| = |r_y| = 1$) and a π phase difference ($\Delta\phi_{xy} = \phi_x - \phi_y = 180^\circ$) along x and y directions under a linear polarization basis (Figures S5 and S6, Supporting Information). By tracking the intersections of curves for equal reflection amplitudes ($|r_x|/|r_y| = 1$, red dotted

Figure 2. MEMS-BMS VWP design ($\lambda = 1030$ nm). a) Calculated complex reflection coefficient r as a function of MS1 nanobrick dimensions $[L_{x1}, L_{y1}]$ under linearly polarized light excitation, for optimizing a half-wave plate designed at $T_{a1} = 465$ nm (MS2 OFF state). b) Calculated complex reflection coefficient as a function of MS2 nanobrick dimensions $[L_{x2}, L_{y2}]$ and orientation $\theta_2 = 45^\circ$ at $T_{a2} = 722$ nm (MS2 ON state), under RCP light excitation. The MS1 nanobrick parameters are set as $[L_{x1}, L_{y1}, \theta_1] = [350$ nm, 130 nm, $0^\circ]$. Note that in the optimal MEMS-BMS VWP design, the MS1 nanobrick dimensions $[L_{x1}, L_{y1}]$ are fixed, while the MS2 geometries $[L_{x2}, L_{y2}]$ and the orientations of both MS1 and MS2 nanobricks $[\theta_1, \theta_2]$ are varied for optimization. c) Calculated reflection amplitudes $r_{1(2)}$ and phases $\phi_{1(2)}$ of the selected MEMS-BMS unit cells under RCP light excitation at $T_{a1} = 465$ nm and $T_{a2} = 722$ nm, respectively. d) Simulated total electric field norm of the designed MEMS-BMS unit cell (#2) in the y - z plane under RCP light excitation at $T_{a1} = 465$ nm and $T_{a2} = 722$ nm, respectively. e) Calculated reflectance of the MEMS-BMS VWP in respective LCP/RCP output channels and corresponding polarization conversion ratio (PCR) $[R_{rcp}/(R_{rcp} + R_{lcp})]$ as a function of the air gap T_a under RCP light excitation.

lines in Figure 2a) and those for the phase difference of $\Delta\phi_{xy} = 180^\circ$, the optimal MS1 nanobrick dimensions were determined to be $[L_{x1}, L_{y1}] = [350, 130$ nm] (red cross markers in Figure 2a), with an optimal T_{SU8} of 470 nm ($\approx 3\lambda_{eff}/4$ of the optical thickness in the SU8 material). Thus the designed MEMS-BMS unit cell exhibits high reflection amplitudes ($|r_x| = |r_y| = 0.95$) and a desired phase difference $\Delta\phi_{xy} = 180^\circ$, indicating that its performance closely approaches that of an ideal HWP, despite the presence of gold material losses. It should be mentioned that this SU8 thickness not only ensures the optimal HWP function but also effectively eliminates the interlayer near-field coupling between the MS1 and MS2 layers,^[39,40] thereby simplifying the design process. Based on the optimized MS1 unit cell and leveraging the modulation principle of Pancharatnam–Berry (PB) phase, the required phase profile ϕ_1 for generating an $l = 2$ vortex beam in the cross-polarized channel can be achieved under RCP light excitation by adjusting the orientation angles of MS1 nanobricks (Figure 2c). Note that the polarization handedness, defined as left-handed circular polarization (LCP) and RCP, is determined by the rotation direction of the electric field vector as observed against the direction of light propagation. Consequently, the vortex phase reflected by the MEMS-BMS VWP is imparted onto the RCP channel.

Building on the designed MS1 arrangements, which feature arrays of nanobricks with identical dimensions and different orientations for eight-level discretized phase profiles to generate $l = 2$ vortex beams, we proceed with the second step of designing the MS2 arrangements. In this case, the MEMS-BMS separation is set to $T_{a2} = 722$ nm ($\approx 3\lambda/4$), corresponding to the “MS2 ON” state, where both MS1 and MS2 unit cells jointly contribute to the overall MEMS-BMS functionality (Figure 2b; Figure 2d, right). It should be noted that the intricate coupling within the MEMS mirror-backed multilayer system induces interactions between the MS1 and MS2 layers, including far-field interference and local-field enhancement effects, which significantly impact the MEMS-BMS response (Figure S7, Supporting Information). Given the designed MS1 unit cells (eight in total) with specific parameters of $[L_{x1}, L_{y1}, \theta_1]$ and $T_{a2} = 722$ nm, we calculated the complex reflection coefficients of the MEMS-BMS as functions of the MS2 nanobrick dimensions $[L_{x2}, L_{y2}]$ and orientations (θ_2) under RCP incident light (Figure 2b; Figure S8, Supporting Information), and optimized the MS2 arrangement for vortex generation with $l = -1$. Notably, the MS2 design incorporates both PB and resonance phases by employing spatially varying nanobrick dimensions and orientations, thereby enabling efficient and polarization-preserving vortex beam generation in the

RCP channel. As an example, Figure 2b shows the optimal selection of MS2 parameters (red cross marker) in the $[L_{x2}, L_{y2}]$ parameter space with $\theta_2 = 45^\circ$, given the predesigned MS1 parameters $[L_{x1}, L_{y1}, \theta_1] = [350 \text{ nm}, 130 \text{ nm}, 0^\circ]$. By individually optimizing each MS2 unit cell $[L_{x2}, L_{y2}, \theta_2]$, based on the previously designed MS1 unit cells, the simulated MEMS-BMS exhibits high reflection amplitudes (≈ 0.90) and required phase ϕ_2 for the generation of vortex beams with $l = -1$ (Figure 2c). The nanobrick dimensions for both MS1 and MS2 are provided in Table S1 (Supporting Information).

Based on the designed MS1 and MS2 unit cells, we constructed the complete MEMS-BMS VWP arrangement for reconfigurable generation of vortex beams with $l = 2$ and $l = -1$ (Figures S9 and S10, Supporting Information). Due to the inherent Fabry–Pérot (FP) nature of the MEMS-BMS configuration, its optical response exhibits a periodic evolution with a period of $\lambda/2$, as a function of the MEMS-BMS separation T_a (Figure 2e).^[41,42] Under normally incident RCP light, the “MS2 OFF” and “MS2 ON” states are effectively achieved at $T_{a1} = 465 \text{ nm} + k_1 \times \lambda/2$ and $T_{a2} = 722 \text{ nm} + k_2 \times \lambda/2$ (k_1 and k_2 are non-negative integers, representing the FP orders), corresponding to the generation of $l = 2$ and $l = -1$ vortex modes in the reflected RCP channel, respectively (Figure 2e). At the lowest FP order ($k_1 = 0$, $T_{a1} = 465 \text{ nm}$; $k_2 = 0$, $T_{a2} = 722 \text{ nm}$), the simulated cross-polarized reflectance (R_{rcp}) of the MEMS-BMS VWP in the RCP output channel reaches 75% and 64%, while the polarization conversion ratio (PCR) [$R_{\text{rcp}}/(R_{\text{rcp}} + R_{\text{icp}})$] achieves 0.95 and 0.87, for generating $l = 2$ and $l = -1$ vortex beams, respectively, demonstrating that the designed MEMS-BMS VWP operates as a highly efficient HWP at the designed wavelength of $\lambda = 1030 \text{ nm}$. As the air gap T_a increases, the efficiency of the MEMS-BMS VWP gradually decreases but remains considerable. For instance, at the fifth FP order ($k_1 = 5$, $T_{a1} = 3040 \text{ nm}$; $k_2 = 5$, $T_{a2} = 3297 \text{ nm}$), R_{rcp} remains at 61% and 53% with PCRs of 0.84 and 0.80 for the two distinct MEMS-BMS operation states, respectively. This slight efficiency reduction is attributed to the enhanced intercell coupling due to the increased MEMS-BMS separations.^[40,42] As far as the wavelength and angular bandwidths of the MEMS-BMS VWP operation are concerned, our simulations indicate that the MEMS-BMS VWP should exhibit a 100 nm wavelength bandwidth (from 980 to 1080 nm) with a high PCR and beam quality in both reconfigurable states (Figure S11, Supporting Information), tolerating oblique incidence angles of up to 7° (Figure S12, Supporting Information).

2.2. MEMS-BMS VWP Fabrication, Assembly, and Characterization

Using electron-beam lithography (EBL), thin-film deposition, and lift-off processes, MS1 and MS2 nanostructures with a 100 μm diameter were sequentially fabricated on a $14 \times 14 \text{ mm}$ SiO_2 substrate. Note that after fabricating the MS1 layer, an SU8 spacer layer was introduced, which was deposited using spin-coating, UV-curing, and hard-baking processes (Figure S13, Supporting Information). The thickness of the SU8 layer, $T_{\text{SU8}} = 463 \text{ nm}$, was measured using white light interferometry (Figure S15, Supporting Information). Figure 3a presents the optical microscopic images of the fabricated BMS, clearly showing that the BMS for

the MEMS-BMS VWP consists of eight equal-sized regions. Four alignment markers at the corners ensure the alignment of the MS2 layer to the MS1 layer during fabrication. The fabricated nanobrick dimensions, orientations, and lateral alignment between the MS1 and MS2 layers were characterized using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Figure 3b shows SEM images at the central region of the MS1 and BMS layers, taken after each fabrication step. It is clearly visible that the MS1 layer features uniformly sized nanobricks with varying orientation angles, while the MS2 nanobricks differ in both size and orientations, aligning with the design specifications. Despite the minor rounded corners of the nanobricks and slightly misalignment between the MS1 and MS2 layers, the fabricated structures closely match the intended design. The MEMS mirror was fabricated following a standard semiconductor micromachining process (Figure S14, Supporting Information). Its precise out-of-plane actuation was enabled by the controlled deformation of four piezoelectric lead zirconate titanate (PZT) membrane cantilevers. Subsequently, the MEMS chip was glued to the SiO_2 substrate containing the BMS and then glued to a printed circuit board (PCB) (Figure 3c). Optical micrographs of the assembled MEMS-BMS VWP clearly show the PZT membrane cantilevers supporting a 400 μm -diameter gold-coated MEMS mirror, above which the circular-apertured BMS is aligned (Figure 3d, front view). Electrical connections were established by wire-bonding the MEMS mirror electrodes to those on the PCB (Figure 3d, back view). After assembly, the electrically tunable MEMS-BMS separation T_a was characterized using white light interferometry (Figure S15, Supporting Information). The initial T_a of the assembled MEMS-BMS is about 2 μm , determined mainly by the size and viscosity of the glue used in the assembly process. With an actuation voltage ranging from 0 to 23 V, the MEMS mirror provides a total tuning range of 1.4 μm , enabling the MEMS-BMS VWP to operate across three adjacent FP orders for an operation wavelength of $\lambda = 1030 \text{ nm}$.

To experimentally characterize the performance of the MEMS-BMS VWP, we built an optical setup comprising a $\lambda = 1030 \text{ nm}$ fiber laser with polarization optics and a complementary metal-oxide semiconductor (CMOS) camera for polarization-resolved measurements (Figure S16, Supporting Information). A quarter-wave plate (QWP) and a polarizing beamsplitter (PBS) were used to analyze the orthogonal circular polarization components (RCP and LCP) of the reflected beams by converting them into orthogonal linear polarization states and spatially separating them into different optical paths. Figure 3e shows the efficiency of the MEMS-BMS component as a function of T_a , varying from 2200 to 3650 nm. Under normally incident RCP light, the reflectance of the MEMS-BMS in the RCP output channel, configured (in the “MS2 OFF” state, k_1 is from 4 to 6) for generating the $l = 2$ vortex beam, is maintained at 70%, with a high PCR of 0.89. Meanwhile, when reconfigured (in the “MS2 ON” state, k_2 is from 3 to 5) to generate the $l = -1$ vortex beam, the reflectance and PCR are 60% and 0.82, respectively. It should be noted that the experimentally achieved performance of the MEMS-BMS VWP closely aligns with simulation expectations, both in terms of key parameters such as reflectance and polarization conversion efficiency, as well as in the dynamic evolution properties during the tuning process (c.f. Figures 2e and 3e). This confirms the robustness and reliability of both our design and fabrication processes, which is

Figure 3. MEMS-BMS VWP fabrication, assembly, and characterization. a) Optical micrograph of the fabricated BMS with a 100 μm diameter, observed in dark-field mode. b) Scanning electron micrographs of the fabricated MS1 (on glass substrate, left) and MS2 (on top of the underlying SU8 and MS1 layer, right) nanostructures in their respective central regions. c) Typical photo of the assembled MEMS-BMS component, consisting of a BMS fabricated on a SiO_2 substrate, glued to a printed circuit board (PCB) with a thin-film piezoelectric MEMS mirror for electrical actuation. d) Detailed optical micrographs of the assembled MEMS-BMS component, showing the piezoelectric lead zirconate titanate (PZT) membrane cantilevers supporting a circular Au-coated mirror that covers the fabricated BMS above. e) Measured reflectance of the MEMS-BMS in respective LCP/RCP output channels and corresponding PCR as a function of T_a under RCP light excitation.

crucial for further optimization of MEMS-BMS components with improved performances and additional functionalities.

The evolution of the transverse mode intensity of the generated beam with the increased actuation voltage was recorded using a CMOS camera (Figure 4a; Video S1, Supporting Information), revealing a gradual and periodic transition between two distinct vortex modes. Specifically, when $V_{m1} = 4.8 \text{ V}$ ($k_1 = 4$) and $V_{m2} = 1.6 \text{ V}$ ($k_2 = 3$), the MS2 layer is reconfigured between the OFF and ON states, facilitating mode switching between $l = 2$ and $l = -1$ vortex beams with donut shapes of different sizes (Figure 4b). Additionally, the phase profiles of the generated vortex beams were verified using the self-interference method,^[31,43] revealing distinct fork-shaped fringes corresponding to the topological charges $l = 2$ and $l = -1$ for the two generated vortex beams. The nonuniform intensity distribution observed in the $l = -1$ vortex beam arises from uneven reflection amplitudes of the MEMS-BMS unit cells when the MS1 and MS2 layers operate together (Figure 2c), where three specific MEMS-BMS unit cells exhibit noticeably higher reflection amplitudes, resulting in a far-field intensity pattern resembling three petals. It can be further mitigated by conducting a joint, though more complex, optimization of both MS layers to achieve uniform reflectance across all MEMS-BMS unit cells in both operational states. High-efficiency and high-contrast switching between the $l = 2$ and $l = -1$ vortex modes, corresponding to distinct MEMS-BMS VWP opera-

tion states, was also demonstrated in intensity profiles recorded within two orthogonal polarization channels (LCP/RCP), with the main reflected power concentrated in the desired RCP channel and minimal residual power in the LCP channel, as shown in Figure S17 (Supporting Information). The dynamic switching process of the two vortex modes was documented by applying a 1 Hz periodic rectangular signal to the MEMS-BMS VWP component (Video S2, Supporting Information). Furthermore, vortex mode purities were evaluated by demodulating the generated beams using an SLM loaded with spiral phase profiles of different topological charges, demonstrating high purities of 90.5% and 86.6% for the $l = 2$ and $l = -1$ vortex modes, respectively, as shown in Figure S18 (Supporting Information). To characterize the response time of the MEMS-BMS VWP component, the reflected beam was modulated using an SLM loaded with a spiral phase profile of $l = -2$, producing modulated beams with central brightness and darkness corresponding to the distinct MEMS-BMS VWP operation states that generate $l = 2$ and $l = -1$ vortex beams, respectively. Then the central part of the modulated beams was filtered using an iris, and intensity contrast measurement corresponding to the two distinct MEMS-BMS VWP functions was recorded with a photodiode detector. The response time, characterized by a fast rise/fall times of 8.9/9.3 μs (Figure 4c), was measured by actuating the MEMS-BMS component with a 1.5 kHz periodic rectangular voltage signal. The demonstrated

Figure 4. MEMS-BMS VWP for fast and reconfigurable vortex beam generation ($\lambda = 1030$ nm). a) Measured evolution of the beam intensity profiles reflected from the MEMS-BMS VWP in the RCP channel as a function of the actuation voltage V_m , under RCP light excitation. b) Measured intensity distributions and self-interference patterns of reflected vortex beams with $l = 2$ ($V_{m1} = 4.8$ V, MS2 OFF) and $l = -1$ ($V_{m2} = 1.6$ V, MS2 ON) in the RCP channel. c) Time response of $l = 2$ and $l = -1$ vortex mode switching measured by actuating the MEMS mirror with a 1.5 kHz periodic rectangle signal.

response is ten times faster than that obtained with our previous MEMS-tunable single-layer MSs,^[31,41,44–46] and comparable to that of state-of-the-art optical MEMS components.^[39] The fast response arises from the increased intrinsic resonant frequency enabled by MEMS mirror miniaturization, which reduces the effective mirror mass while maintaining sufficient mechanical stiffness.

3. Conclusion

In conclusion, leveraging the design flexibility of the BMS and the fine-tuning capability of a thin film piezoelectric MEMS mirror, we achieved high-efficiency dual-state 2D phase control under circular polarization basis, which is enabled by switching the closest to the mirror MS layer between OFF and ON states

at two distinct MEMS-BMS separations. Based on this configuration, we experimentally demonstrated a MEMS-BMS VWP capable of generating switchable vortex modes with $l = 2$ and $l = -1$ under RCP incident light, achieving high polarization conversion efficiency (>80%), high mode purity (>86%), and fast switching speed (9 μ s). It should be emphasized that our MEMS-BMS VWP generates vortex beams with distinct topological charges of opposite signs while preserving other light characteristics, including incident and reflected polarization states, an important feature that favorably distinguishes our approach from approaches imposing inherent constraints between polarization and topological charge conversion.^[43,47] With its high design flexibility, simple control mechanisms, and fast switching time, our MEMS-BMS VWP might find diverse applications in laser machining,^[6,7] advanced imaging,^[8,9] optical tweezers,^[10,11]

dynamic holography,^[48,49] and other adaptive optical systems. Future advancements in material selection, meta-atom geometry design, and optimization algorithms tailored for the MEMS-BMS platform could further enhance its performance and expand its functionalities. Additionally, exploring versatile MEMS actuation modalities, such as tip/tilt, rotation, and variable curvature, is expected to open up new possibilities for the MEMS-tunable MS configurations.^[50,51]

4. Experimental Section

MEMS-BMS Fabrication and Assembly: The MS1 and MS2 layers, each with a 100 μm diameter, were fabricated using EBL, thin-film gold deposition, and lift-off processes twice (Figure S13, Supporting Information). The detailed fabrication processes for each MS layer are as follows: first, a 100 nm-thick poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) A2 layer and a 40 nm-thick conductive polymer layer were successively spin-coated on a SiO_2 substrate ($14 \times 14 \times 0.5$ mm). Subsequently, the MS pattern was defined on the substrate using EBL and then developed in a 1:3 solution of methyl isobutyl ketone (MIBK) and isopropyl alcohol (IPA). After that, a 2 nm titanium adhesion layer and a 50 nm gold layer were deposited using thermal evaporation. Finally, the MS layer was formed after a lift-off process in acetone. Note that the four alignment markers and a continuous gold film measuring $30 \times 30 \mu\text{m}$ were fabricated simultaneously with the MS1 layer to ensure precise alignment during the fabrication of the MS2 layer and to facilitate the calibration of the SU8 layer thickness, respectively, that is, enabling accurate 3D alignment between the MS1 and MS2 layers. After the fabrication of the MS1 layer, a ~ 470 nm-thick SU8 layer was spin-coated over the entire SiO_2 substrate, followed by a soft bake, UV curing, and hard bake process to create a permanent spacer layer. Finally, the MS2 layer was fabricated using the same steps with precise alignment to the MS1 layer, forming the overall BMS.

The MEMS mirror was fabricated using standard semiconductor manufacturing processes (Figure S14, Supporting Information), with additional details being presented elsewhere.^[31,41] Here, a gold MEMS mirror with a 400 μm diameter was selected. The MEMS chip containing the MEMS mirror was glued to the SiO_2 substrate with prefabricated BMS using Loctite 401, and subsequently glued to a PCB. Gold wire bonding between the MEMS mirror and PCB was applied for electrical connection. It is noteworthy that thin-film piezoelectric MEMS actuators have demonstrated robust operational reliability, sustaining over 10^{11} cycles at full 20 V AC actuation at standard conditions (23 $^\circ\text{C}$, 35% relative humidity) with only $\approx 10\%$ positional drift during their lifetime.^[52] Repeatability within ≈ 1 nm for precise air gap control could be achieved through position feedback systems based on optical, capacitive, or piezoresistive sensing techniques.

Numerical Calculations: The simulations of the MEMS-BMS unit cells were performed using the Finite Element Analysis software COMSOL Multiphysics 5.6. Two models were initially constructed: the SiO_2 /gold nanobrick/SU8 structure for the MS1 unit cell and the SU8/gold nanobrick/air structure for the MS2 unit cell (Figure S1, Supporting Information). Periodic boundary conditions were applied in both x - and y -directions to simulate a 2D infinite array, while perfectly matched layers were used in the z direction to truncate the simulation domain. To eliminate the field singularities in the simulation and better represent the fabricated nanostructures, the corners of the nanobricks were rounded with a 5 nm radius. The refractive index of gold was interpolated from the experimental data of Johnson and Christy,^[53] while the refractive index of air, SiO_2 , and SU8 were set to 1, 1.46, and 1.579, respectively. Subsequently, the complex reflection and transmission coefficients of the 2D periodically arranged MS1 and MS2 unit cells were calculated as a function of nanobrick dimensions, under linearly x -/ y -polarized light incidence from either the upper or lower side. Finally, the MS1/MS2 unit cell was integrated with the bottom gold mirror, and the total reflection coefficient r_{tot} can be calculated by decomposing the MEMS-BMS unit cell configuration and applying the FP equation twice.

The performances of MEMS-BMS VWP for vortex beam generation with switchable topological charges were evaluated using FDTD Lumerical Solutions. Perfectly matched layers were used in the x , y , and z boundaries to truncate the simulation domain. Due to the high computational demands, the overall size of the BMS array was scaled down to a diameter of 9 μm (corresponding to 20×20 unit cells), which is smaller than the 100 μm diameter of the fabricated sample. The reflected far-field intensity and phase distributions were projected to orthogonal LCP and RCP channels.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

Acknowledgements

The authors thank Dr. Yangan Zhang at Beijing University of Posts and Telecommunications for insightful discussions on MEMS voltage actuation. This research was supported by National Natural Science Foundation of China (Grant 61905018), Fundamental Research Funds for the Central Universities (Grant ZDYY202102), Beijing Nova Program of Science and Technology (Grant Z191100001119110), Fund of State Key Laboratory of Information Photonics and Optical Communications (Beijing University of Posts and Telecommunications) of China (Grant IPOC2021ZR02), Villum Fonden (Award in Technical and Natural Sciences 2019, Grant 50343 and 37372), Independent Research Fund Denmark (Grant 1134-00010B), Fund of European Union (Grant 101185769-OPTIPATH), China Scholarship Council (Grant 202206470038), and the Research Council of Norway (Grant 323322).

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

C.M. designed the project. C.W., C.M., H.L., and Y.X. performed the simulations. C.W. fabricated the BMS samples. P.C.V.T. assembled the MEMS-BMS component. C.W., H.C., and X.M. constructed the experimental setup and performed the measurement. C.M., L.G., S.I.B., and K.X. supervised the project. C.W. and C.M. drafted the manuscript. All authors discussed the results obtained and contributed to writing up the manuscript.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords

bilayer metasurfaces, half-wave plates, MEMS, tunable optics, vortex beams

Received: June 6, 2025

Revised: July 22, 2025

Published online:

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